

Psychological Outcomes in Survivors of Childhood Cancer and Their Grandparents

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SHORT SUMMARY

Childhood cancer is an illness affecting the entire family unit, including the patients, as well as extended family members such as grandparents. The current thesis aimed to fill the knowledge gap in two overlooked areas of pediatric psycho-oncology: the sexuality of childhood cancer survivors (CCS) and the psychological health of grandparents of CCS. Two different methodologies were applied in three distinct studies for this purpose. The first study used a cross-sectional quantitative design in order to describe the sexuality of CCS in comparison to a reference population and explored the determinants of survivors' sexuality. The second study was a systematic literature review investigating the psychological outcomes in grandparents of children with severe illnesses and summarizing the needed and used psychological support of grandparents. The third study assessed the psychological distress of grandparents of CCS in a cross-sectional quantitative survey and compared the distress of grandparents to the general population. The conducted studies have provided valuable insight into these understudied areas of childhood cancer and allowed for the formulation of recommendations for further research and clinical practice.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CCS	Childhood Cancer Survivor
ChCR	Childhood Cancer Registry
CNS	Central Nervous System
HRQL	Health-Related Quality of Life
ICCS-3	International Classification of Childhood Cancer
PTSS	Post-Traumatic Stress Symptoms
QOL	Quality of Life

CHAPTER 1: Childhood Cancer Overview

Incidence

Childhood cancer is a rare illness that occurs in children between birth and up to 14 years old [1]. Globally, the incidence of cancer in children was estimated to be close to 400.000 new cases every year, accounting for the underreporting practices in low-income countries and the variations in health systems worldwide [2]. In Europe, the incidence in childhood cancer was observed to slowly increase over the last decades [3] and a similar trend was detected in Switzerland as well [4]. The age-standardized incidence has risen in Switzerland from 143 million person-years between 1985 and 1994 to 162 million person-years between 2005 and 2014 [4, 5]. After 2014, an average of 230 new cases of children were diagnosed with cancer every year across the country [6]. The Federal Act on the Registration of Cancerous Diseases enacted in January 2020, requires all cases of children with cancer to be documented into the Childhood Cancer Registry (ChCR) [5, 7, 8]. The ChCR is based on one of the oldest registries in Europe [4, 5] and is responsible for the recording of over 95% of all cases of children with cancer in Switzerland [9]. This practice leads to an effective monitoring of the illness within the country and is essential for cancer surveillance, research, and the developing of new health policies and clinical treatments.

Diagnosis

The etiology of childhood cancer is not well understood [1]. Unlike in adult cancers, where the development of the illness can be linked to unhealthy behaviors or exposure to risky environmental factors, the cause of childhood cancer is still frequently unknown [10]. The diagnosis of childhood cancer is based on the morphology of the tumor, while the

classification of adult cancer relies on the location of the cancer [1, 11]. Childhood cancer is categorized into 12 main groups according to the International Classification of Childhood Cancer (ICCS-3): leukemias; lymphomas; central nervous system (CNS) neoplasms; neuroblastoma; retinoblastoma; renal tumors; hepatic tumors; bone tumors; soft tissue sarcomas; germ cell tumors; other malignant neoplasms and melanomas, other and unspecified neoplasms [11]. In Switzerland, the most frequent types of cancer among children up to the age of 14 are: leukemias (32.8%), CNS tumors (21.9%) and lymphomas (11.7%) [4]. Childhood cancer is more prevalent in children under the age of 4 than in school-aged children, and slightly more boys than girls encounter the illness, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.27 [1, 4, 8].

Treatment

In Switzerland, children diagnosed with cancer are treated in one of the nine existing pediatric oncology divisions located in Aarau, Basel, Bellinzona, Berne, Geneva, Lausanne, Lucerne, St. Gallen and Zurich. The treatment approaches are highly dependent on the specific type and stage of cancer [12]. The most common applied therapies are chemotherapy, radiation therapy, immunotherapy, specialized surgery or a combination of these treatments [13-15]. The treatment of childhood cancer requires an interprofessional approach and involves the collaboration of experts from various fields [10]. To achieve a high standard of care, pediatric oncologists collaborate closely with physicians from other areas of medicine, including pathology, radiology, specialized surgery, as well as with psychologists, nutrition experts, social workers, and case managers.

Survival rates

Despite being a rare illness, childhood cancer remains the second most common cause of death in children in most European countries, following injuries [16]. Since the 1960s, when childhood cancer was rather an incurable illness [14, 15, 17], the 5-year survival rate has constantly increased reaching 81% in Europe between 2010 and 2014 [18]. No differences in survival between girls and boys have been reported for all cancer combined [18, 19]. However, the survival rates vary among countries, with Eastern European countries reporting moderately worse numbers [18-21]. In Switzerland, the observed 5-year survival reached 86.4% between 2009 and 2018, becoming one of the leading European countries in this regard [8].

CHAPTER 2: The impact of childhood cancer on survivors

Despite the positive results in curing childhood cancer and the high survival rates associated with it, cancer treatments are toxic and can have consequences on the health of the children, even long after the end of treatment. An extensive body of research has shown that CCS are at risk of developing various late effects due to their previous illness and its treatments [15].

Physical late effects

CCS are at an increased risk of developing more chronic health conditions than people without a history of cancer. Furthermore, these conditions tend to occur at a faster rate and at a younger age in survivors than in the general population [22-24]. Previous studies have also shown that survivors are at a high risk of developing second cancers [25-29] and have a lower life expectancy than individuals who never had cancer [30]. In addition, CCS may experience hearing difficulties or hearing loss [28, 31, 32], as well as various cardiovascular illnesses [28, 33-35], pulmonary problems [28, 36, 37], fertility and pregnancy complications [38-40], but also impaired cognitive functioning [28].

Psychological late effects

In addition to the physical late effects, the stressful experience of childhood cancer and the exposure to related treatments may impact the mental health of CCS, leading to psychological late effects even years after the cure of cancer. For instance, several studies found decreased overall mental health and lower psychological well-being in CCS when compared to controls [41-44]. CCS were shown to experience increased anxiety and depression [45, 46], more post-traumatic stress symptoms (PTSS) [47, 48] and

higher utilization of mental health-care services [49-51] than comparisons. Furthermore, the health-related quality of life (HRQOL) of survivors was reported to be lower than that of the non-cancer comparison samples [45, 52-54]. Overall, CCS consumed more antidepressant drugs than controls [55, 56] and experienced more suicide ideation than their siblings [57-59]. Other studies, on contrary, found no differences between survivors and the comparison groups in regard to anxiety, depression or psychological well-being [52, 60-62], with one study even reporting lower depression levels in CCS than in the reference population [52]. Similarly, in Switzerland, the average level of distress among survivors was found to be lower than in the norm population. However, despite these positive outcomes, the proportion of Swiss survivors reporting clinical levels of psychological distress was considerably larger than in the general population [63]. Despite the mixed results, it seems that certain subgroups of survivors are at risk for elevated psychological problems [64, 65], in particular female survivors [50, 52-56, 61, 63, 65] and survivors with worse physical health [57, 64, 66].

Socioeconomic late effects

Besides the physical and psychological late effects, CCS may as well encounter socioeconomic difficulties. Depending on the treatment extent and timing, children with cancer are more likely to disrupt their education, repeat school years or use special education programs [65, 67]. Multiple population-based studies have described lower educational attainment for CCS compared to reference populations [68-71], with survivors of CNS cancers reporting the largest contrast [72]. In Switzerland, however, these differences were not observed. Swiss CCS faced challenges during schooling years, but ultimately reached educational levels comparable to the general population, albeit at a

delayed pace [73]. In general, higher percentages of unemployment due to health reasons were found in CCS than in comparisons [74]. The higher risk of unemployment was confirmed in a systematic review of the literature and a meta-analysis for survivors of all cancers, with a particularly elevated risk for CNS cancer survivors [75, 76]. The lower educational attainment and the higher unemployment rates of CCS directly affect their economic situation. Correspondingly, they reached lower income levels and were more likely to access governmental financial assistance than their sibling and the non-cancer populations [77-81]. CCS were also reported to live longer with their parents [82, 83] and to have lower marriage and cohabitation rates than the general population [84-87]. The parental dependence might limit survivors' opportunities in meeting a partner and explore their sexuality. In accordance, survivors described less sexual activity and less experience with sexual intercourse than their peers [88-91].

Sexuality late effects

Sexuality is a fundamental component of human existence, and good sexual health is essential for a person's quality of life (QOL) [92, 93]. However, there is a limited amount of studies investigating if and to what extent childhood cancer can influence survivors' sexuality. The existing literature has described difficulties in multiple areas of sexuality in CCS, with one study reporting that 55% of survivors had experienced at least one sexual health concern in the past month [59].

Psychosexual development

The restricted number of available studies on psychosexual development in CCS described a general delay in reaching normative sexual milestones in CCS compared to the general population [87]. Survivors were older when falling in love for the first time and

when having their first relationship [94-96]. Moreover, survivors' sexual debut occurred at an older age than their peers, with an average delay of 1.2 to 1.6 years [90, 95, 96]. Generally, CCS achieved fewer sexual milestones [95, 97] and reported less sexual partners than the comparison samples [94, 98]. However, two studies have not found these differences [98, 99]. Among the factors associated with survivors' delays, previous research identified higher treatment toxicity [89, 98], surviving CNS cancers [98] and older age at diagnosis as the main determinants [96]. Regarding gender, one study presented mixed results finding delays only in female CCS, while male CCS achieved generally fewer sexual milestones [87].

Sexual functioning

Additionally to psychosexual development, another sexuality area in which survivors might encounter difficulties is sexual functioning. Problems with sexual functioning are defined by low sexual desire, lack of sexual arousal, inability to reach orgasm, reaching orgasm too early and experiencing pain during sexual intercourse [100]. Most of the available literature described more problems with all sexual functioning aspects in CCS compared to the general population [88, 89, 91, 94, 101-103]. The survivors particularly at risk were reported to be of older age [88, 104], of female gender [90, 105, 106], and diagnosed with childhood cancer at an older age [90, 101, 106]. Furthermore, survivors with worse psychological outcomes such as depression, anxiety, or distress [103, 104, 106, 107] and those with reduced physical health and increased fatigue also reported higher sexual functioning issues [106-108]. In addition to the psychological and physical health, survivors' body perception seems to have a strong influence on their sexual functioning as well. Due to cancer treatments, CCS might experience scares after

surgeries, amputation of limbs, general decreased growth, or underdevelopment of certain body areas [28, 109]. They described impaired body image and reported negative perception of their bodies when compared to healthy controls [110-112]. These factors appear to have an impact on survivors' sexual functioning [103, 107] and also on the level of satisfaction with their own sexuality [89, 99, 101].

Sexual satisfaction

While research on CCS and their sexual satisfaction is limited, there is some evidence showing that CCS experience lower levels of satisfaction than comparisons [89, 94, 101]. The factors associated with lower sexual satisfaction in CCS included surviving CNS cancers, having fertility problems, being single and, as previously mentioned, experiencing dissatisfaction with one's own body [89, 90, 94, 99, 101].

CHAPTER 3: Impact of childhood cancer on family members

Impact of childhood cancer on parents

Childhood cancer is a complex illness with impact on all members of the family, not only on the diagnosed child [113, 114]. Parents of children with cancer may experience a high variety of overwhelming emotions and encounter psychological distress and anxiety [115-118]. Research has shown that timing and gender play a role in parental stress. Parents of children going through treatment or of children who experienced a relapse described more distress than parents of children who finished the cancer treatment [115, 117]. In terms of gender differences, mothers were shown to report worse psychological outcomes than fathers [115-118]. However, when examining the psychological outcomes in parents of long-term CCS, research has yielded mixed findings [119]. Some studies reported higher proportions of cases with clinical distress and anxiety in parents than in comparisons [120-122], while others found similar levels of psychological distress, anxiety and HRQOL between parents and the non-cancer populations [122-127]. Nevertheless, studies on PTSS have identified subgroups of parents of CCS with clinically relevant levels of PTSS [128-131]. In a Swiss study, parents of long-term CCS showed comparable degrees of worries and anxiety to the Swiss population, but half of them still reported worries related to their child's former illness [126].

Impact of childhood cancer on siblings

Besides parents, the siblings of the ill child can as well get affected by the cancer related changes in the family. Different systematic literature reviews have described that siblings of children with cancer experienced complex and intense emotions such as jealousy, anger, fear, anxiety, guilt, rejection, loneliness and sadness [132-134]. In general, siblings

received less attention from their parents and witness changes in the family interactions and dynamics [132, 135]. These aspects can lead to impaired child-parent relationships and create long-term problems in the psychosocial development of the siblings [136]. Nevertheless, the difficult situation might also foster increased maturity and empathy levels in siblings [134] and contribute to closer family bounds and intimacy [132].

Impact of childhood cancer on grandparents

Having a child with cancer requires additional care and organization for the parents and, in most cases, leads to disruption of family routines, with families experiencing alterations in their daily activities and changes in the roles and responsibilities of family members [113, 137]. Grandparents have been reported to ease the burden of the family by stepping in to help with administrative tasks, allowing parents to focus on the ill child [138, 139].

Generally grandparents provide substantial support to their families [140, 141]. In Switzerland, 33% of children under 12 years old regularly receive informal care from their grandparents, and in Swiss families without a migration background the proportion reaches 49% [142]. In 2016, the unpaid childcare delivered by grandparents was estimated to reach 8 billion Swiss francs [142]. Grandparents offer valuable assistance to families during regular times, but their help becomes particularly important when one of the children faces an illness [143, 144]. For instance, during cancer treatment, grandparents were reported to help with household chores, visit the ill grandchild in the hospital, accompany them to medical appointments, take care of the healthy siblings and/or the ill grandchild, and even make medical decisions [139, 145-147]. While children undergo treatment, parents might reduce their workload in order to accommodate the needs of the child, which can affect the economic stability of the family [137].

Grandparents were shown to step in and financially assist the parents with some of the cancer-related costs [146, 148]. Besides the instrumental support, grandparents also offer emotional support to the parents by listening to them, encouraging and comforting them when feeling overwhelmed or have lost hope [147].

However, grandparent's support and involvement in the family might come with costs for their mental and physical health. Generally, there is a limited number of studies aiming to understand the impact that cancer might have on children's grandparents. The available literature presented the wide range of emotions that grandparents experienced. Their emotional journey started with the shock of receiving the news that their grandchild has cancer [146, 147, 149, 150]. Afterwards, grandparents described going through a roller-coaster of feelings such as despair, concern, anger, frustrations, helplessness, sadness, disbelief and fear [145-150]. Being afraid was an emotion reported by grandparents even after the cure of the child and their feeling originated in the possibility of cancer recurrence [146, 147]. In addition, grandparents reported more distress, anxiety and depression than grandparents of healthy children [149, 151]. They also consumed more stress-related medication and presented sleep difficulties [149, 151]. One previous quantitative study, investigated risks factors for grandparents and discovered worse psychological outcomes in grandmothers of children with cancer than in grandfathers, but also in grandparents who were unemployed or retired, those who had a granddaughter with cancer, in grandparents with only one grandchild, in paternal kinship and in grandparents who lived far from the ill child [149, 151].

Nevertheless, grandparents also experienced positive outcomes due to their grandchild's illness. For example, they become closer to the other family members, especially the

parents of the ill child and their own partner, and supported each other throughout the overwhelming moments [145-148]. Apart from that, they felt proud of how the parents and the siblings of the ill child managed and coped with stressful situation [146, 148, 150]. Grandparents also described being more grateful for the present moment and life in general [145].

CHAPTER 4: Objectives and aims

There is a lack of knowledge in two important areas of childhood cancer. First, there is a dearth of literature focusing on the sexuality of CCS, especially in the European context. Furthermore, older research assessed sexuality using questionnaires not validated in CCS cohorts. In addition, constructs such as psychosexual development, sexual functioning, and sexual satisfaction were used as interchangeable variables for sexuality, rather than as distinct individual sexuality components. Second, the impact a childhood cancer diagnosis has on the grandparents of the ill children is not well understood. There is very limited research with focus solely on grandparents. To my knowledge, only five studies worldwide inspected the ramifications of the illness on grandparents' psychosocial outcomes. Moreover, there are no available studies conducted on grandparents of CCS, but rather on grandparents of children shortly after the diagnosis or during the treatment. Therefore, the aim of this dissertation was to fill the research gap on these two understudied areas of pediatric psycho-oncology:

- 1) The first objective was to broaden the knowledge regarding the sexuality of survivors and explore which factors might influence their sexual health. In order to reach this goal, the specific aims were to:
 - a) describe the main sexuality outcomes of CCS, i.e. psychosexual development, sexual functioning and sexual satisfaction,
 - b) explore the determinants of these three outcomes, and
 - c) compare the results of CCS to a sample from the general population.
- 2) The second objective of this dissertation was to better understand the psychological health of grandparents of CCS. Therefore, the specific aims were to:

- a) explore the available literature describing the psychological outcomes of grandparents of severely ill children,
- b) summarize the psychological support grandparents of severely ill children needed and used,
- c) describe the levels of psychological distress experienced by grandparents of CCS in Switzerland,
- d) compare their psychological distress to a sample from the general population, and
- e) investigate which factors were associated with grandparents' psychological distress after their grandchildren survived cancer.

CHAPTER 5: Methodology

Different methodologies were used in order to reach the objectives of the current dissertation. For the first objective, a population-based cross-sectional study with a quantitative design was developed. This study was part of a Dutch cohort study that included CCS diagnosed with childhood cancer between birth and the age of 18 years [152, 153]. CCS were identified through the database of the Princess Máxima Center for Pediatric Oncology, which registers and treats all patients with childhood cancer in the Netherlands. After passing the eligibility screening, CCS were extended invitations to participate in the study. Sociodemographic information and sexuality-related questionnaires were collected in a paper and pencil test battery, while cancer-related information was retrieved from the hospital's registry. Survivors outcomes were compared with data on references from the general population, presented in the Dutch national reports [154, 155].

To address the second objective of this dissertation, two distinct methodologies were used. First, a systematic literature review was conducted, which included only original peer-reviewed articles focusing on the psychological outcomes of grandparents of children with a severe physical illness. Due to the limited available literature on grandparents of children with childhood cancer, the topic of the systematic review was expanded from grandparents of children with cancer to grandparents of children with physical illnesses comparable to cancer. All articles were subjected to a quality assessment, and the entire reviewing process was conducted by two independent reviewers. Secondly, a cross-sectional survey study was run, focusing on grandparents of children who survived childhood cancer up to a decade prior to their recruitment. This

study was part of a population-based mixed methods project developed and conducted in Switzerland [156]. Grandparents of eligible CCS were recruited with the help of eight pediatric oncology centers across Switzerland. A representative sample of the Swiss general population was used as comparison. Participants reported sociodemographic information and evaluated their psychological distress in a paper and pencil questionnaire or on an online survey.

CHAPTER 6: Sexuality of childhood cancer survivors

Joint work with Marloes van Gorp, Heleen Maurice-Stam, Gisela Michel, Leontien CM Kremer, Wim JE Tissing, Jacqueline J Loonen, Helena JH van der Pal, Andrica CH de Vries, Marry M van den Heuvel-Eibrink, Cécile M Ronckers, Dorine Bresters, Marloes Louwerens, Sebastian JCCM Neggers, Margriet van der Heiden-van der Loo, Eline van Dulmen-den Broeder, Martha Grootenhuis

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CHAPTER 7: Psychological outcomes of grandparents of severely ill children

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CHAPTER 8: Psychological distress of grandparents of childhood cancer survivors

Joint work with Anica Ilic, Pauline Holmer, Peter Francis Raguindin, Katharina Roser, Eva Maria Tinner, Rebecca Baechtold, Marc Ansari, Manuel Diezi, Elena Lemmel, Freimut H Schilling, Katrin Scheinemann, Gisela Michel

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CHAPTER 9: General discussion

Summary of the main results

Study 1: Sexuality of childhood cancer survivors

The first study aimed to describe the psychosexual development, sexual functioning, and sexual satisfaction of Dutch CCS, to explore the determinants of these sexuality outcomes, and to compare the results of CCS with a sample of the Dutch general population. Survivors reached the normative sexual milestones between the ages of 15 and 18 years old. Among CCS, those who had their sexual debut at a delayed time were male, older, higher educated, survived CNS cancer, and presented lower levels of social and autonomy development. The determinants for worse sexual functioning were female gender, older age, being in a relationship, not having children, lower mental health, negative body perception, and older age at sexual debut. The determinates of lower sexual satisfaction were older age, higher education, no current relationship, lower mental health, and negative body perception. When compared to the Dutch references, CCS reported to have less experience with certain psychosexual milestone such as kissing, petting under clothes, oral, and anal sex. No differences were found between survivors and references regarding their sexual functioning and sexual satisfaction.

Study 2: Grandparents of children with severe physical illnesses

The second study aimed to review the existing literature reporting on the psychological outcomes of grandparents of severely ill children, and to summarize the psychological support grandparents needed and used. For these purposes, 3319 records were screened for eligibility and a total of 12 articles were included in the final analysis. Nine articles reported on studies with a qualitative design, two employed quantitative measures

and one article presented data from a mixed-methods approach. The analysis showed that grandparents of children with severe physical illnesses described a rich variety of feelings and referred to their emotional journey as being on a roller-coaster. The most often mentioned emotion was fear, with grandparents experiencing multiple concerns, including fear for the ill child, the parents of the ill child, the healthy siblings, and even themselves. Moreover, grandparents evaluated their psychological well-being more negatively than the comparison groups. Yet, they almost never accessed professional support services and turned to their family members for emotional assistance. In addition, educating themselves about the child's illness and staying updated about the child's health progress helped grandparents better cope with the stress.

Study 3: Grandparents of childhood cancer survivors

The third study aimed to describe the levels of psychological distress experienced by grandparents of CCS in Switzerland, to compare the distress to comparisons from the Swiss general population, and to determine which factors were associated with grandparents' psychological distress. The analysis revealed that grandparents of CCS experienced average levels of general psychological distress and its three domains: somatization, depression, and anxiety. Moreover, when the grandparents' scores were compared with those of the Swiss general population, their levels did not differ. Furthermore, among grandparents of CCS, those with poorer health perceptions and those who were single reported more psychological distress.

Discussion and interpretation of the results

Sexuality of childhood cancer survivors

Human sexuality is a multidimensional construct in which various personal and sociocultural factors model and influence its course [157, 158]. Specifically for cancer, four types of factors were identified as contributors to sexuality-related problems, i.e. psychological, biologic, interpersonal and sociocultural [108, 157]. As described in Chapter 2, childhood cancer and its treatments can contribute to difficulties for CCS in all four of these areas. Looking at the psychosexual development of survivors in the first study of the current thesis, less experience with normative sexual milestones and delays in sexual debut were observed in CCS compared to the reference group. Interestingly, reduced psychosocial development was identified as an important determinant of these problems. It is possible that an overprotective parental style might influence survivors' psychosocial development by limiting their opportunities for social and sexual experimenting. Literature shows that CCS engage in less social activities and are less likely to live independently from their families [66, 110]. Parents of CCS were reported to be more lenient with their children and, at the same time, more protective than parents of healthy children [159-162]. Their restrictive tendencies seem to stem from their perception of the child as being fragile and vulnerable [161, 163]. When looking at teenagers without a history of cancer, a noticeable delay in reaching normative sexual milestones was also observed in teenagers who experienced more parental monitoring compared to teenagers with less supervising families [164]. Empowering survivors to engage in more social activities and educating parents of CCS about the value of a less restrictive and trusting

setting, might contribute to a healthier social life and increased sexual well-being for survivors.

Concerning determinants of survivors' sexual functioning and sexual satisfaction, several factors were identified as relevant in the first study. For instance, older survivors presented more sexuality difficulties than younger ones. This difference is in alignment with studies on individuals from non-cancer populations who reported greater deterioration in sexuality than younger individuals [165-168]. From previous research it is known that cancer therapies promote premature ageing in survivors, with effects appearing as early as two decades prior than in the general population [169]. Thus, it is plausible that CCS may be more vulnerable to sexuality-related difficulties at an earlier age than the norms, with increasing impairment as they become older. Interestingly, when comparing CCS to references in the first study, no notable differences were found. Due to methodological constraints, the comparison between groups was limited to only participants below the age of 25. It is therefore possible that survivors' difficulties in sexual functioning and sexual satisfactions are not yet noticeable in the early 20s and they will emerge at a later point in life, albeit earlier than in the general population. More research is needed to clarify this aspect, especially studies that including survivors and references of older ages.

In the first study, other factors associated with survivors decreased sexual functioning and sexual satisfaction were shown to be lower mental health and having a negative body perception. In general, a person's mental health can strongly influence their sexuality, not only through medication side effects, but also through mood swings, impaired relationships, social stigma, and reduced sexual desire [92, 170, 171]. In addition,

people's body dissatisfaction may result in avoidance of sexual activity, more discomfort with sexual practices and decreased sexual satisfaction [172-175]. Furthermore, as part of the aging process, individuals experience progressive physical decline resulting in body fragility and development of various chronic illnesses [92]. As discussed in the introduction, survivors are at higher risk of developing multiple chronic illnesses than the non-cancer population, and at an earlier age. Chronic illnesses can affect the sexuality of a person through illness-specific symptoms (pain, immobility), treatment-related aspects (medications side effects, surgeries) and impaired physical function (muscular rigidity, weight fluctuation, urinary incontinence) [92]. The presence of multiple comorbidities in CCS, along with an earlier aging process, increased risk of psychological problems, and also higher body dissatisfaction in CCS than the general population, can create a cumulative burden on their sexuality resulting in impaired sexuality outcomes. In consequence, it is essential to pay attention to the subgroups of CCS at risk and offer them specialized care and treatment options.

Grandparents of childhood cancer survivors

Previous research has described a range of emotions along with decreased psychological wellbeing in grandparents whose grandchildren were going through the acute phase of childhood cancer. Nevertheless, grandparents did not seek specialized professional help due to the lack of available services for grandparents and received emotional support from other family members [148-150]. As shown in the introductory section of this thesis, childhood cancer has an impact on the entire family unit. There is a need to offer access to professional support services to all family members affected by the illness, including

grandparents. Taking care of each member individually will in return ease the overall burden of the family.

Moreover, grandparents reported to have limited knowledge about their grandchild's illness, with some grandparents believing that childhood cancer is incurable and their grandchild will most likely die [147]. One study examined the information needs of grandparents during their grandchild's treatment and reported extensive lack of knowledge regarding various cancer-related aspects, but also information about available support services and how to assist other family members [176]. In addition, studies on grandparents with children suffering from other severe illnesses have shown that being updated about the child's health status helped grandparents to better handle the stress [177, 178]. Informing themselves about the illness of the child enabled grandparents to align their expectations with the reality and resulted in better emotional coping [147]. Therefore, in the acute phase of cancer, it is essential to provide grandparents with information about the type of cancer their grandchild is facing, update them about the child's health progress and guide them towards the available professional support structures. If grandparents' information needs are met, they will feel empowered and more adequately equipped to cope with the overwhelming situation and in return provide better support to the ill child, the parents, and the healthy sibling.

When examining grandparents at a later phase of the cancer, their psychological outcomes were in general positive. In the third study, grandparents of CCS described equivalent levels of psychological distress to the Swiss general population up to a decade after the child's diagnosis. However, subgroups of grandparents were identified to be at risk. Grandparents of CCS with poorer health perceptions and single grandparents

showed increased psychological distress. Previous research has shown that people with physical health conditions are more likely to develop psychological problems such as anxiety and depression [179, 180]. Furthermore, individuals with both physical health conditions and impaired mental health are at higher risk for low QOL and worse physical outcomes [179, 180]. This aligns with the findings of the third study, where grandparents of CCS who perceived their health as worse reported also more psychological distress. It is therefore important to give special attention to grandparents of CCS with health issues and provide them with care options.

Moreover, being single was an additional risk factor identified for psychological distress in grandparents of CCS. During the treatment of their grandchild, grandparents' main emotional support came from their partners, with only isolated cases of grandparents attending professional psychological services. Thus, it might be that single grandparents have overall less support and are therefore at elevated risk of distress. It is important to be considerate of the widowed or divorced grandparents and offer them the possibility to access a support network, potentially in the form of a support group.

All members of families going through childhood cancer are exposed to an enormous burden. Even if the grandparents seem to be doing well long after the diagnosis, there is still a need to pay attention to those who are at risk and offer them support options.

Strengths and limitations

The three studies presented in the current thesis explored highly novel research topics. In Europe, only eight previous studies examined elements of survivors' sexuality, and in some of these studies, sexuality was not the primary research focus, but was rather considered part of survivors' QOL. In the first study, I looked at established constructs of

sexuality in the survivor population, and used questionnaires validated in the CCS cohorts. Regarding the psychological health of survivors' grandparents, no other study worldwide evaluated grandparents' psychological outcomes in a sample consisting solely of grandparents of CCS. The five available former studies explored only the first three years after diagnosis and used combined samples of grandparents of children going through treatment and grandparents of CCS. In the third study, I evaluated the psychological distress of grandparents of long-term survivors and, for the first time in research, assessed them during the first decade after cancer.

All three studies are the result of a multidisciplinary collaboration among various international experts. Professionals from different disciplines contributed to the methodological development of the studies, including researchers, psychologists, specialized physicians, nurses, survivors, and their families. Furthermore, the interprofessional collaboration used in the interpretation of the results led to a holistic understanding of the challenges survivors and their grandparents experience as a result of cancer and was essential in the formulation of recommendations for clinical practice.

Another important strength of the current thesis lies in the use of population-based samples in both cross-sectional studies, and their respective large comparison samples.

However, there are also some limitations to consider when interpreting the findings of the three studies. For instance, the attendance of survivors and grandparents may have been affected by participation bias. Inviting CCS to a study on such a sensitive topic as sexuality and asking them to provide information about certain aspects of their sex lives may have made them reluctant to participate. Moreover, the indirect recruitment of grandparents in the third study depended on the compliance of family members in

forwarding the study information and may have resulted in a decreased sample size. Furthermore, individuals with higher dysfunctionality, both in terms of sexuality and psychological distress, may have refused to participate in the conducted studies due to the increased burden. Thus, it is possible that both cross-sectional studies reported more positive outcomes than the reality. These aspects limit the generalizability of the findings and call for a cautious interpretation of the results.

In the second study, the majority of the research included in the systematic review was qualitative and did not involve comparison samples. Consequently, the review mostly described grandparents' outcomes and was limited in comparison to the general population. Furthermore, systematic reviews are susceptible of publication biases and therefore it is possible that only certain publications were available for evaluation, restricting again the generalizability of the results.

Lastly, the first and third studies, along with all research included in the systematic review, used a cross-sectional retrospective design. This only allows to speculate about the direction of associations between determinants and outcomes, and limits the discussion of causality. As a consequence, future research is recommended to explore these outcomes in longitudinal study designs in order to establish the factors responsible for affecting survivors' sexuality and the psychological outcomes of grandparents of CCS.

Clinical implication

Sexuality of childhood cancer survivors

Body perception appears to play an important role in survivors' sexuality. Tailored interventions addressing body changes of survivors could be implemented in standard healthcare practices and delivered as early as during the treatment phase. Furthermore,

enrollment in physical therapy could improve certain physical functions and, along with specialized psychological counseling, might promote greater body acceptance. Treating survivors' physical alteration holistically and from an early time point could improve their body perception and promote long-term sexual well-being.

In previous research, CCS reported unmet information needs concerning relationships and sexuality, and described lack of information about sex or sexuality from the medical doctors at the treating hospital [91, 181]. Implementing screening for sexuality late effects during regular follow-up visits would be a valuable approach for opening a dialog between CCS and their physicians about sexuality-related problems. In addition, it would offer survivors the opportunity to receive the needed information and discuss possible treatment options. However, healthcare providers often encounter difficulties in addressing sexuality topics and tend to avoid sexuality-related conversation during follow-up consultations [182-184]. Communication training and psychoeducation are therefore needed and recommended for physicians of CCS.

In addition to follow-up clinics, the topic of sexuality could also be addressed in survivors' organizations. Informational materials could be provided and distributed through the internal network of the survivors' organization in regular newsletters. Furthermore, survivors' meetings or support groups moderated by sexologists or onco-psychologists could be organized in order to raise awareness about the existing sexuality problems and provide survivors with treatment options. Addressing such a sensitive topic among CCS peers could encourage sharing among survivors and destigmatize conversations about sexual late effects within the CCS cohort. Previous research found positive associations between survivors' sexuality and their QOL [106]. It is important to normalize the

discussion around sexuality and survivorship, address the specific symptoms, and provide survivors with information and options for care.

Grandparents of childhood cancer survivors

In the acute phase of cancer, grandparents might benefit from additional information. First, they could profit from information regarding the development of the child's illnesses and the changes in their health status. In this regard, clinicians could include grandparents in the information loop and deliver them first-hand information [185]. This approach would keep grandparents updated and would officially make them part of the inner circle, recognizing their importance in the family unit. However, parental consent is required to share medical information and may not always be given. Some research has described relationship challenges between parents and grandparents due to the extensive involvement of the latter [149, 150, 186].

Second, grandparents could be provided with general information regarding their grandchild's illness. Good examples of informational materials tailored to grandparents needs are represented by the booklets developed within the Children's Cancer and Leukaemia Group in the UK and Ireland [187] and within the group coordinated by Wakefield in Australia [188]. These booklets are offered to affected families as part of the hospital's standard information package. They contain information in layman's language about childhood cancer and address questions grandparents might have during the acute phase of the cancer and in the long-term. In Switzerland, these booklets could be used as inspiration and be adapted to the Swiss context. In addition, a grandparents' organization such as "Grandparents of Kids with Cancer – Worldwide", developed by an affected grandmother [189], could also be implemented in Switzerland, perhaps under

the umbrella of the Swiss parents' organization. These informational materials and support organizations could address questions about specific cancer types, provide grandparents with information about how they can help families both instrumentally and emotionally, direct grandparents to local support services, and organize regular meetings and support groups for grandparents. All these tools could help grandparents to better manage the changes and the stress experienced during and after their grandchild's illness. Access to support groups and memberships in grandparent's organizations can also benefit them at later stages of cancer. Being part of such a community would provide grandparents with a support network that they could access if they ever needed it. This would be extremely beneficial especially for grandparents of long-term survivors who do not have access to follow-up meetings with health professionals and psychological counseling as CCS and their parents do.

Conclusion

The present thesis sheds light on two understudied areas of psycho-oncology: the sexuality of CCS and the psychological health of survivors' grandparents.

Sexuality is a fundamental component of human existence, yet the effects of childhood cancer on survivors' sexuality have not received much research attention. My work in the area of sexuality late effects showed that CCS encounter difficulties concerning various aspects of sexuality and identified certain subgroups of survivors with elevated sexuality complications. The current thesis highlights the need to develop and implement holistic interventions for survivors' with impaired sexuality. Nurturing a positive sexual health is essential for a person's QOL. In consequence, integrating these therapies into regular

healthcare services will help survivors achieve adequate sexual health and, in turn, improve their overall well-being.

Despite the extensive involvement and active role grandparents have in the family system, there is a lack of research focusing on them. In my research, I examined grandparents' emotional experiences, individual support needs and psychological health, and identified those at higher risk for negative mental outcomes. There is a demand to extend research and understand the cancer-related effects on all family members, including grandparents. Acknowledging the grandparents' struggles and identifying their support needs and risk factors will help create services especially tailored to their particular situation. Understanding the psychological burden of this forgotten but essential part of the family, and addressing these issues in a professional manner, will prepare grandparents for the psychological challenging circumstances they face. As a result, grandparents will be accordingly equipped to care for the other family members, and the entire family unit will be better able to cope with the extremely stressful situation of having a child with cancer and the challenges that arise during survivorship.

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